

MODELING OF THE ELECTRONIC DOCUMENT CIRCULATION SYSTEM IN RAILWAY CARGO TRANSPORTATION PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT

The article considers the creation of a mathematical model of the electronic document circulation system and processing in the form of three finite sets. The given sets are examined and the relationships between the elements of these sets are determined.

In modern society, there is a process of activation of computing and information technologies in all spheres of activity. The implementation of electronic document circulation and record keeping systems (hereinafter referred to as EDCS) is an urgent task of modern society. Organizations work in different environments, technology is developing at an incredible speed, which leads to an exponential increase in the amount of data. In this regard, it is necessary to use effective tools to conduct research related to management problems and issues, such as modeling. Representation of the processes implemented in the system in the form of a model helps to create a basis for the design of EDCS, which ultimately leads to an increase in management indicators, including efficiency. EDCS systems enables the movement of documents to be a controlled and controlled process, thereby providing high-quality management services. At the same time, the model for evaluating the effectiveness of the introduction of the electronic document circulation system has not been developed.

Design, development, implementation and evaluation of EDCS systems use formal models that allow the use of measurable objects that can be applied to mathematical apparatus.

Graph and automata theory are examples of the use of formal models in evaluating EDCS implementation.

Work flow model using graph theory Z.V. Alferov and M. Yu. It was one of the first proposed in the case of the Krukovskys. Foreign scientists have considered the use of automata to model the information interaction of working groups [2]. Automata have been used by other authors to model a connected system of interacting processes in solving process control problems. [3].

A document cycle can be formally expressed as three finite sets and a link between the elements of these sets.

The mathematical representation of this process can be expressed in the form of ternary:

$$D_T = \{U, D, F\} \quad (1),$$

Here is $\{D_T\}$ - Official model of EDCS, $\{U\}$ - set of participants, $\{D\}$ - a set of actions, $\{F\}$ is a set of document states, i.e., a document cycle is a set of document states by a set of participants is the implementation of sets of actions.

$\{Y\}$ set is defined as a limited set of roles that can be assigned to actual participants in a workflow.

$\{D\}$ - defined as a limited set of actions that can be performed in the EDCS system in question.

$\{F\}$ set — $\{U\}$ Participant in the set $\{D\}$ A finite set of states that documents can take after performing the actions in the set.

Let's take a closer look at each set.

A set of participants $\{U\}$ also refers to a set of roles that participants perform in the EDCS system.

To define the set of roles of the participants, it is necessary to use the labor rules existing in the $\{U\}$ organization, which reflect the actions that the employees perform. Therefore, under the participants of the set we mean the list of tasks performed by the employee.

All employees in a workflow perform multiple roles. At the same time, the same role can be suitable for several employees at the same time.

This combination allows you to formalize and detail the requirements that the organization imposes on its employees, and also allows you to create criteria for the effectiveness and success of a particular employee.

A set of states $\{F\}$ in an EDCS system defines a finite set of discrete representations of a document, each of which is one of the possible states of the document in its life cycle.

The EDCS system model can be represented by two types of document flow: predefined document flow and situational document flow.

Establishing a model of an EDCS system is called a predefined document cycle if the set of EDCS cases is the definition of all possible cases that are acceptable and necessary in the EDCS.

The situational document cycle of the EDCS system model indicates that new situations may arise during process development.

The triple sets of both types of workflow can be represented by $\{U, D, F\}$.

$\{F\}$ The elements of the set are determined by determining the forms of acceptable documents, which include electronic versions of paper documents identified during the

analysis of the EDCS system and new forms related to the internal needs of the external EDCS system.

$\{F\}$ a collection of cases is usually called an album of forms. It is assumed that the album of forms defined and described in the analysis phase is approved by the user of the EDCS system, and changes during the development of the EDCS system, the conformity of the album of forms and cases used by EDCS is controlled.

$\{F\}$ The criterion for the success of the formalization of the set is its completeness and the compatibility of the simulated EDCS system, that is, after the synthesis and programming of the EDCS model, there cannot be a situation where the document should be submitted to a state that is not an element of the set $\{F\}$.

In the analysis of the created EDCS system, the relationships between the states of document circulation are identified and documented. Workflow logic is presented as a sequence of actions that cause the EDCS system to change from one state to another. As a result, the sequence of connected actions is synthesized, the documents are transformed from the initial states to the required (final) states, and this is the set $\{D\}$.

When synthesizing real EDCS models, it is often difficult to separate the actual document cycle processes into a set of clearly separated discrete processes. The identified difficulties are primarily related to the subjective component of the idea of document circulation. This leads to the fact that the various specialists involved in the document cycle have a unique understanding of the documents and the roles of the process participants. A multiplicity of ideas creates a multiplicity of realizations and contradictions. As a result, synthesized models are cumbersome and poorly controlled.

$\{D\}$ By the definition of a set, we understand that the occurrence of an action is an event that causes a change in the state of at least one document. Thus, it is possible to combine multiple representations by combining one-way links that connect the same states.

In addition, it is clear that each state of the document requires a certain strobe event for its occurrence, that is, an action must occur in the EDCS system that causes this state to occur. Thus, it can be argued that the success criterion for defining a set $\{D\}$ is the association of elements in the set $\{F\}$.

$\{U, D, F\}$ after we consider each of the sets, it is possible to prove that there are relations between the elements of the sets that determine the connections between them. Relationships can exist between different elements of the same collection or between elements of different collections.

An example of a relationship between the elements of a set is a causal relationship between the states of the set $\{F\}$. The definition of document turnover roles, i.e., the influence of participants on specific situations that lead to their change, is determined by the ratio of the element in the set $\{U\}$ to the elements in the set $\{F\}$.

Thus, it can be argued that the relationship between the elements of the set determines the relationship, their totality determines the complete list of business processes of the organization, which predetermines the possibility of fully implementing the EDCS system.

Two types of relationships are used to represent relationships - one-to-one and one-to-many. In theory, it is possible to use multiple relationships, but in practice it is not intended, because it complicates the perception of the model and its work logic. If for some reason it is

necessary to use it, then this type of connection can be synthesized using the previous two types [4-6].

Thus, the EDCS system is defined as three collections, each of which contains a limited number of elements and the possibility of changing the contents of the collections during the life cycle of workflow processes. The transformation of elements occurs discretely in such a way that each stage of transformation corresponds to the system $\{U, D, F\}$ with a static composition of sets. A set of triples $\{U, D, F\}$ describes the events that occur in the workflow system with respect to time.

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